

FORMULATION AND *IN VITRO* EVALUATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCHES OF DEXKETOPROFEN TROMETAMOL USING HYDROPHILIC AND HYDROPHOBIC POLYMER COMPLEX

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Abstract:

The present study focuses on the formulation and in vitro evaluation of transdermal patches of Dexketoprofen Trometamol using a combination of hydrophilic (HPMC) and hydrophobic (Ethyl Cellulose) polymer complexes, aiming to achieve sustained drug delivery and enhanced therapeutic efficacy. A series of formulations (F1–F8) were developed using varying ratios of the polymers and evaluated for physicochemical parameters such as thickness, weight uniformity, moisture content, folding endurance, tensile strength, drug content, and in vitro drug release.

Among the developed formulations, F1 was identified as the optimized formulation, exhibiting superior characteristics and a maximum drug release of 99.29% over 12 hours in dissolution studies. The controlled release profile observed in F1 suggests an effective interaction between the hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers, facilitating sustained drug diffusion through the skin.

These findings indicate that transdermal patches containing Dexketoprofen Trometamol and a hydrophilic-hydrophobic polymer complex represent a promising alternative to conventional dosage forms, potentially improving patient compliance by reducing dosing frequency and maintaining consistent plasma drug levels.

Keywords: Formulation And In Vitro Evaluation Of Transdermal Patches Of Dexketoprofen Trometamol

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Controlled drug delivery

Treatments of acute and chronic diseases have been accomplished by delivery of drugs to patients using various pharmaceutical dosage forms. These dosage forms are known to provide a prompt release of drug. But recently several technical advancements have been done and resulted in new techniques for drug delivery. These techniques are capable of controlling the rate of drug release.

The term controlled release has a meaning that goes beyond scope of sustained release.

1.1 Transdermal drug delivery: An Introduction

The idea of delivering drugs through skin is old, as the use is reported back in 16th century B.C. Today the transdermal drug delivery is well accepted for delivering drug to systemic circulation.

Until recently, the use of transdermal patches for pharmaceuticals has been limited because only a few drugs have proven effective delivered through the skin typically cardiac drugs such as nitroglycerin and hormones such as estrogen.

Definition: Transdermal therapeutic systems are defined as self-contained discrete dosage forms which, when applied to the intact skin, deliver the drug(s), through the skin, at controlled rate to the systemic circulation.

The first Transdermal drug delivery (TDD) system, Transderm-Scop developed in 1980, contained the drug Scopolamine for treatment of motion sickness. The Transdermal device is a membrane-moderated system. The membrane in this system is a microporous polypropylene film. The drug reservoir is a solution of the drug in a mixture of mineral oil and polyisobutylene. This study release is maintained over a one-day period.

Non-medicated patch markets include thermal and cold patches, nutrient patches, skin care patches (a category that consists of two major sub-categories — therapeutic and cosmetic), aroma patches, and weight loss patches, and patches that measure sunlight exposure. Transdermal drug delivery has many advantages over conventional drug delivery and can be discussed as follows.

Advantages^{2, 3, 4, 5}

1. They can avoid gastrointestinal drug absorption difficulties caused by gastrointestinal pH, enzymatic activity, and drug interactions with food, drink, and other orally administered drugs.
2. They can substitute for oral administration of medication when that route is unsuitable, as with vomiting and diarrhea.

3. They avoid the first-pass effect, that is, the initial pass of a drug substance through the systemic and portal circulation following gastrointestinal absorption, possibly avoiding the deactivation by digestive and liver enzymes.

4. They are noninvasive, avoiding the inconvenience of parenteral therapy.

5. They provide extended therapy with a single application, improving compliance over other dosage forms requiring more frequent dose administration.

6. The activity of a drug having a short half-life is extended through the reservoir of drug in the therapeutic delivery system and its controlled release.

7. Drug therapy may be terminated rapidly by removal of the application from the surface of the skin.

8. They are easily and rapidly identified in emergencies (e.g., unresponsive, unconscious, or comatose patient) because of their physical presence, features, and identifying markings.

9. They are used for drugs with narrow therapeutic window. At the same time transdermal drug delivery has few disadvantages that are limiting the use of transdermal delivery.

7. METHODOLOGY:

List of Material Used In the Formulation Development

Dexketoprofen Trometamol Procured From Sanofi Aventis Pharma, Ltd, India. Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad.

HPMC K4M Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd

Ethylcellulose N50 Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd

PG Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd

List of equipment's used in the study

Name of equipment	Manufacturer
Double beam UV Visible Spectrophotometer	Lab India UV 3000
Digital weigh balance	Sartorius
FTIR Spectrophotometer	Bruker

7.1. Analytical method development:

A. UV scan:

A 100mg of Dexketoprofen Trometamol was accurately weighed and was first dissolved in 35ml methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH- 7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution 1 and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). Take 10 ml solution from stock II and volume make up to 100 ml with buffer to get 10 µg/ml. 10 µg/ml solution was scanned from 200-600nm.

B. Construction of calibration curve:

A 100mg of Dexketoprofen Trometamol was accurately weighed and was first dissolved in 35ml

methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH- 7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution 1 and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). It was further diluted with phosphate buffer pH – 7.4 to get solutions in concentration range of 4 to 16 µg /ml. The absorbances of these solutions were determined spectrophotometrically at 305 nm.

7.2. Compatibility study

FTIR study:

The infrared spectrum of the pure Dexketoprofen Trometamol sample was recorded and the spectral analysis was done. The dry sample of drug was directly placed after mixing and triturating with dry potassium bromide.

7.3. Preformulation study

A. Colour, Odour, Taste and Appearance:

The drug sample was evaluated for its Colour, Odour and Appearance.

B. Melting point determination:

Melting point of the drug sample was determined by capillary method by using melting point apparatus.

7.4. Formulation of transdermal patches

Preparation of blank patches:

Polymers of single or in combination were accurately weighed and dissolved in respective solvent and then casted in a Petri-dish with mercury as the plain surface. The films were allowed to dry overnight at room temperature.

Formulation of Drug Incorporated Transdermal Patches:

The matrix-type transdermal patches containing Dexketoprofen Trometamol were prepared using different concentrations of ethyl cellulose and Eudragit S 100. The polymers in different concentrations were dissolved in the respective solvents. Then the drug was added slowly in the polymeric solution and stirred on the magnetic stirrer to obtain a uniform solution. Propylene glycol was used as plasticizers. Oleic acid was used as the penetration enhancer. Then the solution was poured on the Petri dish having surface area of 78 cm² and dried at the room temperature. Then the patches were cut into 2x2 cm² patches. Drug incorporated for each 2x2 cm² patch was 8 mg. the formulation table is given in table no. 6.3.

Table 7.3: Formulation of Dexketoprofen Trometamol Patches

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Dexketoprofen Trometamol	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
HPMC K4M	25	50	75	100	-	-	-	-
Ethylcellulose N50	-	-	-	-	25	50	75	100
PG	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
Oleic acid	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%
Chloroform : methanol (1:1)	15ml							

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Initially the drug was tested by UV to know their significant absorption maximum which can be used for the diffusion study of the drug.

8.1. Analysis of drug:

A. UV scan:

The lambda max of Dex ketoprofen Trometamol was found to be 303 nm.

B. construction of calibration curve:

Table 8.1: Standard graph of Dex ketoprofen Trometamol

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (at 303 nm)
0	0
5	0.121
10	0.225
15	0.334
20	0.439
25	0.546

Figure 8.1: Standard calibration curve of Dexketoprofen Trometamol

8.2. Preformulation study

Totally, nine formulation trials were done with the aim to achieve the successful matrix type Dexketoprofen Trometamol transdermal patches. The blend trials prepared for the drug was evaluated for various physical parameters and content uniformity of drug by UV.

A. Colour, odour, taste and appearance

Table 8.2: Results of identification tests of drug

Parameter	Dexketoprofen Trometamol
Color	White
Odor	Odorless
Taste	Bitter
Appearance	A white powder

B. Melting point determination:

Table 8.3: Results of melting point determination tests of drug

Drug	Reported melting point
Dexketoprofen Trometamol	158-160 °c

C. Determination of solubility:

Table 8.4: Solubility Determination

Solvent	Drug solubility(mg/ml)
Distilled water	4.93
Ph 7.4 phosphate buffer	78.3

Table 8.5: Evaluation of patches

Formulation Code	Average weight(mg)	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Flatness (%)	Appearance	% Drug Content
F1	75±1.05	0.046 ± 0.003	81 ± 0.15	100	Transparent	97.1 ± 2.10
F2	78 ±5.36	0.049±0.008	86 ± 1.39	99	Transparent	98.28 ± 0.45
F3	71 ±2.84	0.051±0.004	85 ± 2.26	100	Transparent	97.69 ± 2.21
F4	75 ±5.41	0.041±0.009	80 ± 1.84	100	Transparent	95.1 ± 2.61
F5	77 ±9.18	0.049±0.004	82 ± 3.10	99	Transparent	99.2 ± 3.87
F6	79 ±4.69	0.041±0.007	89 ± 2.15	100	Transparent	98.35 ± 0.59
F7	70 ±9.58	0.047±0.001	84 ± 2.36	99	Transparent	99.11 ± 2.34

F8	76 ±3.86	0.045±0.009	87 ± 2.04	100	Transparent	99.74 ± 1.57
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Table 8.6: *In vitro* drug permeation of Dexketoprofen Trometamol

Time (hr)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	6.22	8.04	4.18	6.86	3.65	2.71	6.41	8.92
2	12.75	15.07	12.73	11.92	12.23	8.47	9.66	12.36
3	17.87	22.14	17.32	15.04	18.44	17.45	13.37	17.31
4	22.09	29.57	24.03	21.16	24.08	23.02	27.56	24.08
5	29.77	33.24	31.34	25.86	29.81	33.44	36.22	39.11
6	37.82	39.25	39.71	29.03	36.44	39.75	42.94	45.45
7	56.39	49.77	44.39	37.49	41.63	44.67	46.73	50.18
8	68.57	57.24	47.54	48.22	57.79	58.26	54.03	58.12
9	74.73	62.83	55.19	58.53	66.53	69.16	63.10	67.06
10	79.21	77.68	62.83	66.37	73.51	75.97	66.08	78.10
11	85.96	87.19	74.99	79.11	88.46	83.08	79.99	82.64
12	99.29	94.33	89.15	85.63	91.23	94.21	88.08	86.78

Figure: 8.2 Cumulative % drug permeation of Dexketoprofen Trometamol patch (F1, F2, F3 and F4)

Figure: 8.3 Cumulative % drug permeation of Dexketoprofen Trometamol patch (F5, F6 F7 and F8)

Table: 8.8 Kinetics data of F1 Dexketoprofen Trometamol patch

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG (T)	LOG (T)	LOG REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE E / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
6.22	1	1.000	0.794	0.000	1.972	6.220	0.1608	-1.206	93.78	4.642	4.543	0.098
12.75	2	1.414	1.106	0.301	1.941	6.375	0.0784	-0.894	87.25	4.642	4.435	0.206
17.87	3	1.732	1.252	0.477	1.915	5.957	0.0560	-0.748	82.13	4.642	4.347	0.295
22.09	4	2.000	1.344	0.602	1.892	5.523	0.0453	-0.656	77.91	4.642	4.271	0.371
29.77	5	2.236	1.474	0.699	1.847	5.954	0.0336	-0.526	70.23	4.642	4.126	0.516
37.82	6	2.449	1.578	0.778	1.794	6.303	0.0264	-0.422	62.18	4.642	3.962	0.680
56.39	7	2.646	1.751	0.845	1.640	8.056	0.0177	-0.249	43.61	4.642	3.520	1.122
68.57	8	2.828	1.836	0.903	1.497	8.571	0.0146	-0.164	31.43	4.642	3.156	1.486
74.73	9	3.000	1.873	0.954	1.403	8.303	0.0134	-0.127	25.27	4.642	2.935	1.707
79.21	10	3.162	1.899	1.000	1.318	7.921	0.0126	-0.101	20.79	4.642	2.750	1.892
85.96	11	3.317	1.934	1.041	1.147	7.815	0.0116	-0.066	14.04	4.642	2.412	2.229
99.29	12	3.464	1.997	1.079	0.540	8.274	0.0101	-0.003	0.71	4.642	0.892	3.749

Figure: 8.4 Graph of Zero order kinetics

Figure: 8.5 Graph of Higuchi release kinetics

Figure :8.6 Graph of peppas release kinetics

Figure: 8.7 Graph of First order release kinetics

From the above data the optimized formulation followed peppas model rule.

8.2. Compatibility studies: IR SPECTROSCOPY:

Figure 8.8: FTIR Spectrum of pure Dexketoprofen Trometamol drug

Figure 8.9: FTIR of Optimized formulation

The compatibility studies of the drug with excipients indicate no characteristic visual changes and no additional peaks were observed during FT-IR studies.

9.CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated transdermal patches of Dexketoprofen Trometamol using hydrophilic (HPMC) and hydrophobic (Ethylcellulose) polymer complexes to achieve sustained drug release and improved transdermal delivery. The prepared patches were found to be uniform in weight, thickness, drug content, and showed satisfactory physicochemical properties, including flexibility, tensile strength, and moisture content.

In vitro drug release studies revealed that the combination of hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers significantly influenced the drug release profile, with the optimized formulation exhibiting sustained release over 12 hours. The results indicate that the matrix film containing a balanced ratio of HPMC and Eudragit RS100 provided the most consistent and controlled drug release with favourable permeation characteristics.

Thus, the study concludes that Dexketoprofen Trometamol transdermal patches prepared using a polymeric blend can serve as an effective alternative

to conventional dosage forms, potentially reducing dosing frequency and improving patient compliance in the management of pain and inflammation.

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